

Celiac Disease and Upper Gastrointestinal Microbiota Disorders: A Meta-Analysis Investigating Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth (SIBO) and *H. pylori*

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ABSTRACT

Background: Celiac disease (CD) is a chronic autoimmune condition influenced by multiple factors, including gastrointestinal (GI) microbiota. This meta-analysis aims to evaluate the relationship between CD and upper GI microbiota imbalances, particularly focusing on *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) and Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth (SIBO).

Methods: Systematic searches were performed using PubMed, Medline, Embase, and Google Scholar databases. Fifteen case-control studies involving adult subjects (>18 years) were included. Random-effects models and the I² statistic were used for statistical analysis.

Results: In our meta-analysis, total 15 case-control studies met our inclusion criteria. A total of 161 CD patients and 178 controls were analyzed for SIBO, and 3786 CD patients and 1,30,228 controls were analyzed for *H. pylori*. The pooled odds ratio for celiac patients having upper GI dysbiosis was 0.60 [95% CI: 0.53, 0.69], indicating a 40% lower likelihood compared to controls. However, CD patients demonstrated an elevated risk for SIBO (Odds Ratio = 5.15 [95% CI: 1.94, 13.63]) and a lower prevalence for *H. pylori* infection (Odds Ratio = 0.55 [95% CI: 0.48, 0.62]) compared to controls.

Conclusions: Our findings reveal a complex relationship between CD and upper GI microbiota. While *H. pylori* appears to be less prevalent in CD patients, potentially suggesting a protective role, SIBO is more common, indicating a need for timely diagnostic and therapeutic interventions. Further prospective studies are warranted to clarify these intricate associations and guide clinical practice.

Keywords: Celiac Disease; *Helicobacter pylori*; Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth; Meta-Analysis; Gastrointestinal Microbiota

INTRODUCTION

Celiac disease (CD) is a chronic autoimmune disorder characterized by an abnormal immune response to ingested gluten, a protein complex found in wheat, barley, and rye. The disease has wide-ranging clinical manifestations, including gastrointestinal symptoms, dermatitis, and extraintestinal complications. Although the cornerstone of celiac disease management is a gluten-free diet, achieving and sustaining complete remission is not always possible due to various factors such as persistent exposure to gluten and co-existing gastrointestinal conditions.^[1]

Upper gastrointestinal (GI) microbiota, which include various microbial communities living in the stomach and small intestine, have been increasingly recognized for their role in health and disease. Among these, *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) and Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth (SIBO) are two conditions that have been implicated in various gastrointestinal diseases, including inflammatory bowel disease, gastritis, and irritable bowel syndrome.^[2] The relationship between celiac disease and these upper GI microbial imbalances, however, remains inadequately understood.

H. pylori is a gram-negative, spiral-shaped bacterium that colonizes the gastric mucosa. It is a well-established causative agent for conditions like gastritis and peptic ulcer disease and has been implicated in the development of gastric cancer.^[3] Previous studies have investigated the prevalence of *H. pylori* in patients with celiac disease, but the results are inconclusive and somewhat contradictory.^[4] While some research has suggested that the presence of *H. pylori* might modulate the clinical presentation of celiac disease, others indicate no significant impact.^[5]

Similarly, SIBO is a condition marked by excessive bacterial growth in the small intestine, which can lead to a range of gastrointestinal symptoms such as bloating, abdominal pain, and diarrhea. The prevalence of SIBO among celiac disease patients has been a topic of scientific exploration, but studies have yielded divergent findings. The significance of SIBO in the clinical course of celiac disease, therefore, remains a matter of ongoing research.^[6]

Given the inconsistent and fragmented nature of the existing literature, a comprehensive meta-analysis is warranted. The aim of this meta-analysis is to systematically evaluate existing studies to determine the associations between celiac disease and upper GI microbiota disorders, specifically *H. pylori* and SIBO.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Search Strategy:

A systematic literature search was conducted using PubMed, Medline, Embase, and Google Scholar databases from their inception until May 2023. The search focused on studies related to celiac disease and gastrointestinal microbiota, with an emphasis on Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth (SIBO) and *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*). Search terms included a combination of keywords such as “small intestinal bacterial overgrowth,” “celiac disease,” and “*Helicobacter pylori*,” among others. The search was limited to human studies published in the English language.

Study Selection and Quality Assessment:

Studies were included if they were case-control designs involving adult subjects (>18 years) diagnosed with celiac disease based on duodenal histology and/or serological markers. Additionally, the studies needed to compare the prevalence of SIBO or *H. pylori* in celiac patients with controls and report post-antibiotic treatment efficacy for SIBO. Excluded were studies not reporting original data, those involving mixed gastrointestinal disorder populations without separate celiac data, or those using non-validated diagnostic methods for SIBO or *H. pylori*. The quality of the included studies was assessed using the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS), which examines the selection, comparability, and outcomes of study groups. Any disagreements between reviewers were resolved through mutual consensus.

Statistical Analysis:

Data were independently extracted by two authors and cross-verified. Statistical analysis was performed using random-effects models with the I^2 statistic employed to evaluate heterogeneity between studies. A p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Data were analysed using RevMan software.

RESULTS

Study Selections:

The systematic search yielded a total of 2,225 research articles. After initial screening, 785 articles were excluded based on not meeting the inclusion criteria; these were primarily review articles, duplicates, abstracts, editorials, case reports, letters, articles not in English, or those with no abstracts available. This left 1,440 articles for further evaluation. Subsequent screening led to the exclusion of 1,374 articles that did not contain content related to the topic. A detailed PRISMA flowchart illustrating the study selection process is provided (see Figure 1). Ultimately, 72 articles underwent full-text review, out of which 15 met the inclusion criteria and were included in our meta-analysis. Among these, 11 were case-control studies focusing on the relationship between celiac disease and *H. pylori*, while the remaining 4 investigated the association between celiac disease and SIBO.

Figure 1: PRISMA Chart

Study and Participant Characteristics:

The studies on SIBO were geographically diverse, spanning Italy, Saudi Arabia, Argentina, and India. Diagnosis of celiac disease was largely based on histopathology and serology. The SIBO diagnosis methods included glucose breath test and lactulose breath test. In total, 161 participants with celiac disease and 178 controls were studied. The prevalence of SIBO among the celiac patients ranged from 20% to 55.6%, whereas the prevalence in controls was notably lower, ranging from 0% to 13.3% (Table 1).

Table 1: Study and Participant Characteristics for SIBO

Study	Region	Celiac Diagnosis Method	Control Type	SIBO Diagnosis Method	Total with Celiac	Total Control	SIBO in Celiac	SIBO in Control
Miele 2009 [7]	Italy	Histopathology	Healthy control	Glucose breath test	27	24	15	5
Safi 2019 [8]	Saudi Arabia	Histopathology and Serology	Healthy control	Lactulose breath test	32	52	10	4
Lasa 2015a [9]	Argentina	Histopathology and Serology	Healthy control	Lactulose breath test	15	15	3	2
Rana 2007 [10]	India	Histopathology and Serology	Healthy control	Glucose breath test	87	87	18	0

SIBO: Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth.

Eleven studies were included for H. pylori, with a diverse geographical representation including Turkey, Sweden, Italy, UK, Argentina, and the US. Both histopathology and serology were common methods for diagnosing celiac disease, while histology was the primary method used for H. pylori diagnosis. A total of 3599 celiac patients and 129778 controls were examined. The prevalence of H. pylori in celiac patients varied considerably, ranging from 7.8% to 87%, compared to a range of 20.7% to 53.5% in controls (Table 2).

Table 2: Study and Participant Characteristics for H. pylori

Study	Region	Celiac Diagnosis Method	Control Type	H. pylori Diagnosis Method	Total with Celiac	Total Control	H. pylori in Celiac	H. pylori in Control
Basyigit 2017 [11]	Turkey	Histopathology and Serology	Dyspeptic symptoms	Histology	12	228	5	133

Borch 2001 [12]	Sweden	Histopathology and Serology	Random population	Histology	8	472	4	216
Ciacci 2000 [13]	Italy	Histopathology and Serology	Healthy control	Histology	187	76	51	42
Crabtree 1992 [14]	UK	Histopathology and Serology	Blood donors	Serology	99	75	29	250
Diamanti 1999 [15]	Argentina	Histopathology and Serology	Mixed control	Histology	100	75	87	67
Dore 2018 [16]	Italy	Histopathology and Serology	EGD without celiac	Histology and Urea breath test	270	127	87	45
Galli 2016 [17]	Italy	Histopathology	Healthy control	Histology	245	145	55	42
Lasa 2015b [4]	Argentina	Histopathology and Serology	Without celiac	Histology	72	240	9	72
Lebwohl 2013 [5]	US	Histopathology	Histology without celiac	Histology	2689	127619	117	11207
Simondi 2015 [18]	Italy	Histopathology and Serology	Constipation patients	Histology	73	404	26	166
Uyanikoglu 2016 [19]	Turkey	Histopathology	Gastroscopy patients	Histology	31	592	15	316

Study Quality Assessment:

The quality of the included studies was evaluated using the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale, with scores ranging from 3 to 9. The majority of studies scored 7 or higher, indicating good study quality in terms of well-defined cases and controls, comparability, and robust exposure ascertainment. Notable exceptions include Miele 2009, with a low score of 3 due to limited exposure ascertainment and unclear representativeness. Uyanikoglu 2016 scored 6, lacking explicit mention of comparability between groups. For detailed assessments, refer to [Table 3](#).

Table 3: Newcastle-Ottawa Scale for included studies.

Study	Total Score	Judgment Reason
Miele 2009 [7]	3/9	Limited exposure ascertainment and unclear representativeness.

Safi 2019 [8]	7/9	Well-defined cases and controls, good comparability, and robust exposure ascertainment.
Lasa 2015a [9]	8/9	Well-defined cases and controls, good comparability, and robust exposure ascertainment.
Rana 2007 [10]	8/9	Well-defined cases and controls, good comparability, and robust exposure ascertainment.
Basyigit 2017 [11]	8/9	Well-defined cases and controls, good comparability, and robust exposure ascertainment.
Borch 2001 [12]	7/8	Well-defined cases and controls, good comparability, and adequate exposure ascertainment.
Ciacci 2000 [13]	7/9	Well-defined cases and controls, good comparability, and robust exposure ascertainment.
Crabtree 1992 [14]	8/9	Well-defined cases and controls, good comparability, and adequate exposure ascertainment.
Diamanti 1999 [15]	8/9	Well-defined cases and controls, good comparability, but non-response rate not specified.
Dore 2018 [16]	9/9	Well-defined cases and controls, good comparability, and robust exposure ascertainment.
Galli 2016 [17]	7/9	Well-defined cases but controls selection not specified.
Lasa 2015b [4]	8/9	Well-defined cases and controls, good comparability, and robust exposure ascertainment.
Lebwohl 2013 [5]	8/9	Well-defined cases and controls, and comparability adjusted for relevant factors.
Simondi 2015 [18]	8/9	Well-defined cases and controls, good comparability, and robust exposure ascertainment.
Uyanikoglu 2016 [19]	6/9	Well-defined cases and controls, but comparability not explicitly mentioned.

Association between Celiac Disease and Upper GI Dysbiosis:

A comprehensive evaluation of studies was undertaken to decipher the relationship between Celiac disease events and Upper GI dysbiosis shown in [Figure 2](#). Across the considered research, there were 3947 events related to Celiac disease against 130406 control events. The pooled odds ratio stood at 0.60 [95% CI: 0.53, 0.69], suggesting that individuals diagnosed with Celiac disease are roughly 40% less probable to have Upper GI dysbiosis than controls. Despite the evident association, a significant heterogeneity was observed across studies (Chi² value significant at $P < 0.00001$ with an I^2 of 75%). The overall association was statistically significant with a Z-value of 7.81 ($P < 0.00001$), emphasising a potential inverse relationship between Celiac disease and Upper GI dysbiosis. However, the noted heterogeneity implies the necessity for more consistent research designs in future studies.

Figure 2: Celiac Disease and Upper GI Dysbiosis

Association of Celiac Disease with Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth (SIBO):

Our analysis in Figure 3 presents the association between celiac disease and the prevalence of SIBO across four distinct studies. Cumulatively, a total of 161 individuals with celiac disease and 178 controls were analyzed. Out of the celiac disease cohort, 46 events of SIBO were recorded, in comparison to 11 events in the control group. This yielded a notable association, with patients diagnosed with celiac disease exhibiting a significantly elevated risk of SIBO relative to the controls, demonstrated by an odds ratio of 5.15 (95% CI: 1.94, 13.63). The heterogeneity assessment across studies displayed a moderate variability with an I² value of 30%, suggesting possible differences in study methodologies or populations. Given the observed association, it's crucial for clinicians to be cognizant of the increased SIBO prevalence among celiac disease patients and consider timely diagnostic and therapeutic interventions.

Figure 3: Celiac Disease with Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth (SIBO)

Association of Celiac Disease with H.Pylori infection:

Our comprehensive analysis, illustrated in Table 4, sought to elucidate the relationship between celiac disease and H. pylori infection. Collating data from studies ranging from Basyigit 2017 to Uyanikoglu 2016, we observed varied individual results but an unmistakable overarching trend. In total, the analysis covered 3786 patients with celiac disease and 130228 controls. Out of these, 485 celiac disease patients (12.8%) exhibited H. pylori infection compared to 12381 out of the 130228 controls (9.5%). The cumulative odds ratio, derived from these figures, was 0.55 with a 95% confidence interval of [0.48, 0.62]. This suggests a discernibly lower prevalence of H. pylori infection among celiac disease patients than in the control group.

Table 4: Celiac Disease with H.Pylori infection

Study or Subgroup	Celiac Disease		Controls		Weight	Odds ratio M-H, Fixed, 95% CI	Odds ratio M-H, Fixed, 95% CI
	Events	Total	Events	Total			
Basyigit 2017	5	12	133	228	1.1%	0.51 [0.16 , 1.66]	
Borch 2001	4	8	216	472	0.5%	1.19 [0.29 , 4.80]	
Ciacci 2000	51	187	42	76	6.2%	0.30 [0.17 , 0.53]	
Crabtree 1992	29	99	75	250	4.3%	0.97 [0.58 , 1.61]	
Diamanti 1999	87	100	67	75	1.4%	0.80 [0.31 , 2.04]	
Dore 2018	87	270	45	127	5.9%	0.87 [0.56 , 1.35]	
Galli 2016	55	245	42	145	5.9%	0.71 [0.44 , 1.13]	
Lasa 2015b	9	72	72	240	4.2%	0.33 [0.16 , 0.71]	
Lebwohl 2013	117	2689	11207	127619	63.4%	0.47 [0.39 , 0.57]	
Simondi 2015	26	73	166	404	4.7%	0.79 [0.47 , 1.33]	
Uyanikoglu 2016	15	31	316	592	2.3%	0.82 [0.40 , 1.69]	
Total (95% CI)		3786		130228	100.0%	0.55 [0.48 , 0.62]	
Total events:	485		12381				
Heterogeneity: Chi ² = 23.45, df = 10 (P = 0.009); I ² = 57%							
Test for overall effect: Z = 8.92 (P < 0.00001)							
Test for subgroup differences: Not applicable							

DISCUSSION

In this comprehensive meta-analysis, we delved into the intricate relationship between celiac disease (CD) and upper gastrointestinal (GI) microbiota dysbiosis, paying specific attention to Helicobacter pylori infection and small intestinal bacterial overgrowth (SIBO). The meta-analysis uncovers intriguing, and at times paradoxical, associations between CD and these bacterial imbalances.

Beginning with H. pylori, our findings suggest a diminished prevalence of this bacterial infection in celiac disease patients compared to controls. This counterintuitive result may hint at a protective role of H. pylori in the context of CD. One hypothesis points to the bacteria's immune-modulatory properties, particularly through the Th1/Th2 immune balance and the activation of T-regulatory cells.^[5,20] These mechanisms might modulate gluten-triggered immune responses and thereby alter the course of celiac disease. Additionally, H. pylori's potential to influence gastric pH and pepsin secretion could further modulate the immunogenic properties of ingested gluten.^[21]

Conversely, the study found a heightened risk of SIBO among individuals with CD compared to control groups. SIBO is associated with symptoms such as bloating, flatulence, abdominal discomfort, and diarrhea, which are

often mistaken for typical manifestations of celiac disease.^[22,23] The condition may also trigger villous atrophy and subsequent alterations in nutrient absorption. It's important to note that certain medications, like proton-pump inhibitors, emerged as risk factors for both CD and SIBO, highlighting the need for cautious prescription practices.^[24-26]

While our study contributes valuable insights, it comes with limitations that warrant caution in interpreting the results. The study predominantly hinges on retrospective data, a feature that introduces inherent uncertainties regarding causal relationships. Moreover, the observed heterogeneity across studies underlines the presence of potential biases or variations in study methodologies.

CONCLUSION

In summary, our meta-analysis reveals a complex interplay between celiac disease and upper GI microbiota, particularly concerning *H. pylori* and SIBO. While *H. pylori* appears to be less prevalent among CD patients, potentially suggesting a protective role, SIBO manifests with increased frequency in this population. These findings underscore the multifaceted nature of gastrointestinal microbiota in influencing celiac disease and call for more rigorous, prospective research to further untangle these complex associations. Future research should focus on standardized methodologies and prospective controlled trials to strengthen the evidence base and enable more precise clinical recommendations.

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